

Optimizing Target-Setting for Performance Indicators in Development: Approaches and Best Practices

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines target-setting methods for performance indicators in the development sector and their role in monitoring progress, evaluating impact, and supporting strategic decision-making. It argues that many development organizations rely on simplistic approaches, such as linear projections or arbitrary targets, which fail to reflect contextual realities and the complexity of social change. To address this gap, the paper reviews established target-setting practices and the challenges affecting their effectiveness.

The study draws on theoretical frameworks including goal-setting theory, theory of change, and results-based management to support more adaptive and meaningful target-setting processes. These approaches enable organizations to establish realistic and sustainable targets aligned with development priorities.

The paper emphasizes the need for evidence-based and participatory target-setting that incorporates stakeholder engagement, ethical considerations, and continuous learning. It proposes an adaptive management framework that allows for periodic reassessment and adjustment of targets in response to changing conditions and emerging data. The study contributes to development effectiveness discourse by offering an integrated framework for setting targets that better captures the complexities of social change and sustainable development.

1. Introduction and Background

Establishing effective performance indicators and targets is crucial for monitoring progress, evaluating outcomes, and driving improvements across various sectors. A performance target is a specific, planned/expected level of indicator result to be achieved within a particular period. Targets help determine whether progress is being made against project implementation. They can be used to measure performance, support learning, and provide accountability.

The development sector lacks precise target-setting methods for performance indicators. The sector often relies on simplistic linear projections, arbitrary increases, or overly ambitious, donor-goal-focused approaches that sometimes ignore contextual realities. Adjustments are haphazard without a process; others never made adjustments. Unhinged adjustment undermines the credibility of the target. An improved target-setting process is essential for better target management.¹

Although target-setting methods such as benchmarking, historical trend, expert judgment, and stakeholder engagement are widely used, there is no standardized, integrated, and context-sensitive framework for combining them in complex settings. Current approaches remain fragmented and often rely on simplistic projections or single methods, overlooking context, non-linear change, data constraints, and donor-driven pressures. As a result, targets are often unrealistic or weakly justified, undermining decision-making, accountability, and learning. This creates a clear need for a coherent, evidence-based, and adaptive framework for setting credible and achievable performance targets in development contexts.

The target-setting process within the Total Performance Management Framework is a collaborative, evidence-based, and data-driven approach for defining an organization's goals over a specific timeframe. It utilizes the organization's strategic direction to establish anticipated outcomes, guide planning efforts, and inform programmatic decisions, while ensuring transparency between investment decisions and performance expectations. Quality data and robust analyses are essential to support sustainable target setting, which connects organizations' actions to results and enhances accountability.²

This paper critiques the absence of methodological target-setting in development, which erodes credibility, decision-making, and resource allocation. It examines current practices, identifies challenges, and proposes innovative, adaptive approaches, rooted in a holistic framework, to enhance target accuracy, relevance, and impact. Ultimately, it advocates nuanced, dynamic methods with regular reassessments to navigate the complexities of social change and advance sustainable development goals.

2. Methodology: Literature Review Approach

This study adopts a structured narrative literature review to examine existing approaches to target-setting for performance indicators in the development sector. Relevant literature was identified through a comprehensive search of peer-reviewed journal articles, institutional guidelines, and grey literature from leading development actors, including multilateral organizations, bilateral agencies, and international NGOs. Key sources included publications from organizations such as the World Bank, USAID, OECD, UNDP, and Heifer International,

¹ Daniel Green et al., *Setting Targets in an Asset Management Performance Measurement Framework* (Jiuzhaigou, Sichuan, China: Delft University of Technology Press, 2016), 2.

² Federal Highway Administration, *TARGET SETTING Component of Transportation Performance Management* (Washington, D.C.: Federal Highway Administration, 2016), 2.

as well as academic works on monitoring and evaluation, results-based management, and performance measurement. The selection of literature was guided by relevance to target-setting methodologies, theoretical frameworks (e.g., goal-setting theory, theory of change, and results-based management), and practical applications within development contexts. Priority was given to recent and widely cited sources, alongside foundational texts that provide conceptual grounding. The review employed a thematic analysis approach, organizing the findings into key methodological categories, including benchmarking, expert judgment, historical trend analysis, stakeholder engagement, and forecasting. These themes were then critically synthesized to identify patterns, strengths, limitations, and gaps in current target-setting practices. This approach enabled the development of an integrated and adaptive framework grounded in both theory and practice.

3. Definition of Key Terms

To mitigate the equivocation fallacy, keywords are defined or rephrased parts of your argument to avoid ambiguity.³

3.1. Monitoring and Evaluation

Monitoring involves collecting necessary information with minimal effort to make timely steering decisions. Monitoring is an ongoing process integrated into the project cycle to ensure that programs do the 'right things' correctly to improve quality. It provides early indications of progress or lack thereof, helping to continuously improve project design and implementation.⁴

Monitoring supports management decisions by providing data to compare actual performance with original plans. According to the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development's (OECD) Development Assistance Committee, monitoring is a continuous function that systematically collects data on specified indicators to inform management and stakeholders about the progress toward and achievement of objectives, as well as the use of allocated funds.⁵

Program evaluation assesses the collective value of multiple projects, examining the utility of their activities and strategies, often deferring full reviews until later while collecting annual interim data. In contrast, project evaluation focuses on a single project within the program, including its critical components, to gauge goal achievement and the project's contribution to overall success or failure.⁶

3.2. Target-Setting

Key Performance Indicators are short-term performance benchmarks that help businesses track their progress toward achieving broader goals. Targets are specific operational measures that indicate whether objectives are being met, like increasing customer acquisition by 20%.⁷

Target Setting is the use of baseline data, information on possible strategies, resource constraints, and forecasting tools to collaboratively establish a quantifiable performance level that the agency aims to achieve within a specific time frame. Targets link investment decisions and performance expectations transparently across all stakeholders.⁸

³ Anand Jayprakash Vaidya and Andrew Erickson, *Logic & Critical Reasoning: Conceptual Foundations and Evaluation Techniques* (Dubuque, IA: Kendall Hunt, 2011), 38–39.

⁴ Patrick Gudda, *A Guide to Project Monitoring & Evaluation* (Bloomington, IN: AuthorHouse, 2011), 6.

⁵ The Government of Ghana, *NATIONAL MONITORING AND EVALUATION MANUAL* (Accra - Ghana: The Government of Ghana, 2014), 19.

⁶ Gudda, 56.

⁷ Daan Van Beek, "A Complete Guide on How to Set Smart KPI Targets and Goals," June 2024, 1, <https://www.rib-software.com/en/blogs/kpi-targets-goals-examples>.

⁸ Federal Highway Administration, *TARGET SETTING Component of Transportation Performance Management*, 1.

Targets define specific, time-bound performance levels based on established performance indicators. They can either set a minimum acceptable level of performance or outline aspirational goals for improvement.⁹ A performance target is a specific, quantifiable, planned, or expected level of indicator result to be achieved within a particular period. Targets are necessary to determine the degree of progress against the project's expectations from the start of the design phase. They can be used to measure performance, learning, and accountability.¹⁰

3.3. Key Performance Area and Key Performance Indicator

Key Performance Areas in the development sector are essential domains that directly contribute to achieving development goals. They are strategically identified focus areas that align with an organization's mission and objectives, serving as the foundation for setting specific, measurable targets and indicators to track progress and evaluate the success of development programs. By concentrating on these critical areas, organizations can ensure overall effectiveness and maximize the impact of their initiatives.¹¹ A KPI is a quantifiable measure used to evaluate the success of an organization, employee, or project in meeting performance objectives. KPIs provide a way to track progress, identify areas for improvement, and make data-driven decisions.¹²

3.4. Result-Based Management

The OECD defines RBM as a management strategy whereby all actors, whether directly or indirectly involved in achieving a set of results, ensure that their processes, products, and services contribute to achieving the desired results (outputs, outcomes, and higher-level goals or impact). The strategy focuses on achieving results at all levels and clearly articulates the cause-and-effect relationships among inputs, activities, outputs, outcomes, and effects.¹³ UNDP sees it as a management strategy that uses feedback loops to achieve strategic goals. This approach ensures that the processes, outputs, and services are geared towards achieving desired outcomes and impacts. RBM includes using performance information to improve decision-making and program performance.¹⁴ The World Bank views RBM as a strategy to improve management effectiveness and accountability by focusing on results. It involves using evidence to inform decision-making and emphasizes planning, monitoring, and evaluating all aspects of a program or initiative to ensure that goals and objectives are met.¹⁵

4. Understanding Performance Indicators and Their Importance in the Development Sector

Performance indicators are essential in the development sector as quantifiable metrics that measure progress, effectiveness, and impact of interventions, offering tangible evidence of change across economic, health, social, and

⁹ Ali Nabeela, Guidelines for Setting Performance Targets at District Level (Islamabad, Pakistan: Pakistan Initiative for Mothers and Newborns, 2008), 4.

¹⁰ Heifer International, "Setting Targets Guidelines" (Heifer International, June 2021), 4.

¹¹ Usmani Fahad, "Key Performance Area (KPA)," PM Study Circle (blog), November 17, 2022, 1, <https://pmstudycircle.com/key-performance-area-kpa/>.

¹² Culligan and Sherriff, Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning for Development Professionals Guide, 29.

¹³ Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), Glossary of Key Terms in Evaluation and Results-Based Management (Paris: OECD Publications, 2002), 33, <https://www.oecd.org/dac/evaluation/2754804.pdf>.

¹⁴ United Nations Development Program (UNDP), HANDBOOK ON PLANNING, MONITORING AND EVALUATING FOR DEVELOPMENT RESULTS (New York, NY 10017, USA: United Nations Development Program (UNDP), 2009), 10, <http://www.undp.org/eo/handbook>.

¹⁵ Designing a Results Framework for Achieving Results: A How-to Guide (Washington, DC: World Bank, 2012), 7.

environmental benchmarks. They enable development agencies, NGOs, and governments to monitor project outcomes, ensure accountability, and demonstrate the value of their initiatives. In an evidence-based era, these indicators guide policy decisions, justify funding, and amplify benefits for target communities.

Establishing performance indicators and targets requires legitimacy to ensure practical effectiveness. The three key criteria for designing indicators are validity and reliability, functionality, and legitimacy, with the latter influencing acceptance through achievable, clear targets that balance ambition and attainability. Legitimacy considers supply-side constraints, such as legal and resource limits, while highlighting project managers' roles in shaping indicators.¹⁶

Performance indicators are crucial in project management and general business contexts, emphasizing the importance of well-designed targets and strategic KPI tracking. Working with KPIs offers numerous benefits in the broader business context, including consistent progress tracking, improved efficiency and productivity, enhanced performance and collaboration, data-driven strategic planning, and a competitive edge through continuous growth. These aspects underscore the need to balance ambition and achievability in target setting, the value of clear and legitimate goals, and the benefits of KPI tracking for organizational success. Well-implemented performance indicators and targets thus serve as powerful tools for driving performance, fostering growth, and achieving long-term objectives across various sectors.¹⁷

Outcome KPIs are indicators that assess the results of circular processes, programs, and operating models at the company level and should be used for public target setting. These KPIs are supported by circular design, waste production, transparency, product life extension, and output collection. KPIs measure a company's progress toward establishing circular processes and are essential for achieving Outcome KPIs throughout the value chain. These include metrics related to circular design, waste reduction, product utilization, and post-use waste collection. KPIs are crucial for tracking a company's transition to more sustainable practices and enhancing its efforts.¹⁸

Setting targets aims to drive improvement by assessing actual performance against expected outcomes, enabling necessary interventions and adjustments to resource allocation. Target setting assists front-line project managers in prioritizing areas for improvement, motivates staff to achieve specific performance milestones, fosters a sense of ownership, and contextualizes broad objectives for local relevance. Target setting should not be viewed in isolation; it requires readiness to improve performance, a supportive environment, and a monitoring system to track progress. Overall, practical target setting is integral to performance management and can significantly enhance the quality and accessibility of services.¹⁹

Identifying the right KPIs is essential to business success, focusing on metrics that drive growth and goal achievement. To select KPIs effectively, organizations should ensure that KPIs are directly linked to the organization's overall objectives, influence decision-making, and are quantifiable with specific timeframes for measurement. Limiting the number of KPIs

¹⁶ Green et al., *Setting Targets in an Asset Management Performance Measurement Framework*, 4.

¹⁷ Beek, "A Complete Guide on How to Set Smart KPI Targets and Goals," 1–2.

¹⁸ The Circular Economy Indicators Coalition, "Corporate Circular Target-Setting Guidance" (Geneva, Switzerland, 2023), 10.

¹⁹ Nabeela, *Guidelines for Setting Performance Targets at District Level*, 5–6.

tracked to maintain clarity and focus is advisable, with an emphasis on high-impact, easily understood indicators. Organizations must continuously evaluate and adjust their KPIs as business conditions evolve to remain relevant and aligned with strategic goals. This structured approach helps organizations make informed decisions, enhance performance measurement, and foster employee engagement and accountability.²⁰

Selecting indicators, determining baselines, and setting targets is vital for program cycle monitoring, using a manageable set of well-defined indicators aligned with funder requirements, organizational goals, and local priorities to enhance data quality and minimize collection burdens. The process involves identifying indicators, assembling stakeholder teams, conducting baseline assessments, and conducting regular reporting to ensure reliable, relevant targets throughout the project lifecycle.²¹

USAID's Journey to Self-Reliance framework aims to enhance development outcomes and reduce dependency on foreign assistance by utilizing the Program Cycle for strategic planning and partnerships. Within this framework, setting targets is essential for assessing progress against established expectations and serves as an accountability mechanism for operational units and missions. Targets help focus efforts on achieving specific goals, justify implementation decisions, link budgets to results, and motivate stakeholders. When actual performance deviates from targets, it provides an opportunity to investigate necessary adjustments in design or implementation. Overall, targets are vital for measuring

performance, alongside evaluation and learning processes, and for facilitating a structured approach to achieving development goals.²² The USAID Program Cycle is a continuous framework that integrates constraints, programmatic processes, learning, adaptation, and results to enhance development outcomes. Targets play a vital role in monitoring and evaluation (M&E), serving as accountability mechanisms that help assess progress toward achieving results.²³

For example, goals typically focus on measurable outcomes such as increasing school enrolment rates, reducing dropout rates, and enhancing the quality of education by improving student learning outcomes. Policymakers are encouraged to establish schooling and learning targets and to implement policies that monitor relevant learning indicators, thereby necessitating robust system-level assessments. Effective learning targets should be ambitious yet attainable and aligned with students' expected competencies at various educational stages.²⁴

Target setting is crucial as it provides clear direction, a timeline, and a pathway for achieving organizational goals. It fosters a common language among staff and departments, motivating teams to align resources effectively, adapt their work processes, and strive for growth and transformation. Without established targets, organizations risk stagnation. Setting targets enhances communication, sets expectations, monitors progress, generates enthusiasm, ensures stakeholder buy-in, and promotes creativity and development. Target setting is essential for driving organizational success and

²⁰ Joshua Otieno Owuor, "7-Step Guide to Setting KPI Targets," Bold BI by Syncfusion (blog), April 27, 2023, 3, <https://www.boldbi.com/blog/7-step-guide-to-setting-kpi-targets/>.

²¹ Heifer International, "Setting Targets Guidelines," 6–7.

²² USAID, "TARGET SETTING GUIDE" (USAID, December 2020), 7.

²³ USAID, 7.

²⁴ Luna-Bazaldua Diego et al., "Checklist for Setting Targets for Progress in Reducing Learning Poverty and Improving Developmental Reading Subskills," 2020, 3.

facilitating continuous improvement.²⁵ Effective KPI targets boost organizational performance and goal achievement by providing data-driven insights to support decision-making and continuous improvement. They align staff on priorities, enable progress tracking, enhance motivation through visible contributions, foster accountability, and optimize resources to improve efficiency and gain a competitive edge.²⁶

Performance measurement and target-setting are vital for organizational growth. Once KPIs are established, setting performance targets clarifies objectives for all and makes strategic visions more manageable and actionable. This structured approach enhances accountability and facilitates communication and alignment within the organization, ultimately driving improved performance and fostering a culture of continuous improvement.²⁷

KPI targets are essential for aligning individual and team efforts with broader organizational goals, as they define success in measurable terms. By establishing specific targets, organizations can transform the often-vague concept of success into concrete objectives, such as increasing sales by a certain percentage or improving customer satisfaction scores. This clarity guides data-driven decision-making rather than intuition, enabling organizations to allocate resources effectively and adjust strategies as needed. Ultimately, KPI targets foster a culture of continuous improvement by providing a framework for performance evaluation and accountability across the organization.²⁸

5. Theoretical Frameworks that Underpin Target-Setting

The Goal-setting theory, developed by Locke and Latham, emphasizes that conscious goals regulate human behavior and that specific, challenging goals lead to higher performance than vague or easy objectives. The key findings of the theory include that performance is directly linked to goal difficulty when there is commitment and that specific goals consistently outperform general "do your best" goals. Goals influence performance by directing attention, energizing effort, increasing persistence, and motivating strategy development. Factors enhancing goal commitment include the importance of goal attainment and self-efficacy. Feedback on progress is crucial for effectiveness, and goals and self-efficacy mediate the impact of other motivational variables. While group goal setting can benefit interdependent tasks, it may impair performance on complex tasks. The theory has significant implications for management practices, including performance appraisal and training. It highlights the importance of self-regulation through goal setting in achieving high performance and fostering a cycle of success.²⁹ This theory underscores the need to set performance targets in all development initiatives.

The Goal-setting theory posits that specific, challenging goals lead to better performance than vague or easily attainable ones. For example, instead of setting a vague goal like "improve community health," a specific target such as "reduce child mortality by 20% within three years" provides a clear,

²⁵ ASA Research, "S.M.A.R.T. Target Setting Guide," ASA Research (blog), 2022, 2, <https://www.asa-research.com/2022/08/31/smart-targets/>.

²⁶ Owuor, "7-Step Guide to Setting KPI Targets," 2.

²⁷ Info Entrepreneurs, "Measure Performance and Set Targets," Info Entrepreneurs (blog), 2019, 3, <https://www.infoentrepreneurs.org/en/guides/measure-performance-and-set-targets/>.

²⁸ Ted Jackson, "How to Set KPI Targets: 9 Steps to Drive Results," Clear Point Strategy (blog), August 2024, 2, <https://www.clearpointstrategy.com/blog/how-to-set-kpi-targets>.

²⁹ Henry L. Tosi, Edwin A. Locke, and Gary P. Latham, "A Theory of Goal Setting and Task Performance," *The Academy of Management Review* 16, no. 2 (April 1991): 2–30.

measurable objective that can more effectively direct attention and resources. Challenging goals foster greater effort and persistence. Therefore, goals built on this theory should be both realistic and challenging. A key component of goal-setting theory is providing feedback to individuals or teams working toward the goal. Regular feedback on progress in development projects is essential for maintaining momentum and allowing for adjustments. Development projects must be flexible enough to respond to changing realities, especially in volatile environments like post-conflict zones or disaster recovery areas. Therefore, setting target processes should allow for adjustments based on feedback, such as after baseline and midterm evaluations.

The implications of the goal-setting theory for real-world development projects are profound. Developing practitioners can drive more effective and sustainable outcomes by setting specific, challenging performance indicator targets, fostering goal commitment, incorporating regular feedback, and enabling self-regulation. In practice, this means creating a structured, evidence-based goal-setting approach. This approach motivates stakeholders and ensures that the goals remain adaptive to the dynamic challenges of development work. By carefully applying goal-setting theory, performance indicator targets can transform from abstract benchmarks into powerful drivers of meaningful change.

Another central framework that supports target setting is the theory of change. Using a theory of change helps organizations systematically analyze the complex, interconnected factors underlying development challenges. By articulating the root causes of these challenges and making explicit assumptions about how proposed strategies will yield results, a theory of

change provides a framework for learning and adaptation throughout programming cycles. This approach allows for necessary adjustments based on evidence and feedback, ensuring that strategies remain relevant, especially in response to changing circumstances. The theory of change fosters collaboration among stakeholders by clarifying differing perspectives and assumptions, leading to stronger partnerships and improved coordination in achieving common objectives. The theory of change is a vital tool for maximizing the impact of development change by guiding strategic planning and decision-making.³⁰ This further guides most development work, establishing the theory within which change will occur and how to measure it. Ensuring this framework guides target setting helps build quality targets into the indicators.

To focus entirely on the targeting setting, it is relevant to understand results-based management. RBM is a management approach widely adopted in the public sector. It aims to enhance performance and accountability by focusing on achieving specific results. Originating from public-sector reforms in the 1980s, RBM emphasizes the importance of M&E for informing decision-making and improving program effectiveness. It integrates planning, monitoring, and evaluation functions to encourage a culture of results. RBM offers a valuable framework for promoting systematic learning and improving organizational performance in the pursuit of development goals.³¹

Another theoretical framework that guides target setting is the collaborative framework. The collaborative framework for target setting involves three guiding principles and four general stages to enhance the process. The principles include

³⁰ UNDAF, "THEORY OF CHANGE. UNDAF COMPANION GUIDANCE" (UNDAF, 2022), 5.

³¹ Markiewicz and Patrick, *Developing Monitoring and Evaluation Frameworks*, 55–57.

collaboration, which emphasizes gathering relevant information and engaging key stakeholders in discussions; documentation, which encourages stakeholders to record decisions, assumptions, and findings throughout the process; and socialization, which focuses on sharing insights and progress with all parties involved. The four stages of the target-setting process are setting the indicator, preparing the stage, establishing the target, and reviewing and revising as necessary. This structured approach ensures that all stakeholders are aligned and informed throughout the target-setting process, ultimately leading to more effective outcomes.³²

A results framework guides target-setting by structuring the expected outcomes of projects/programs and mapping inputs to outputs (goods/services), outcomes (population benefits), and impacts (long-term changes) through cause-and-effect linkages. It clarifies objectives, incorporates measurable indicators/baselines/targets for evidence-based M&E and adjustments, boosts stakeholder engagement through shared hypotheses, and enhances accountability to achieve strategic goals.³³

Target-setting uses a systematic M&E approach, building on results frameworks and developing logical framework matrices that list indicators. Form a stakeholder team (M&E staff, project managers) to recommend targets through timed planning sessions that review indicators and analysis methods; set initial targets pre-baseline, and adjust post-assessment with documented reasons (possibly renegotiating with donors), ensuring relevance and achievability. The process supports flexible, hierarchical/nonlinear methods (top-down

or bottom-up), factoring in coherence across strategies, projects, and activities to enable effective measurement of success and learning.³⁴

Achieving targets is an essential indicator for managers overseeing the progress of strategies, projects, or activities. If targets are quickly met, they may not provide meaningful insights into project performance. A deviation of more than 10% from a target prompts an investigation into the underlying reasons, including flawed assumptions, technical issues, or shifts in priorities. Setting targets is guided by a collaborative framework consistent with USAID's Program Cycle, allowing for flexibility in approach, whether top-down or bottom-up. Managers must consider various factors when establishing targets, including the need for improvement and the organization's capacity for change. While indicators and targets are essential for measuring success, they should also be complemented by broader narratives that capture developmental trends and contextual changes. This comprehensive approach ensures that target setting drives accountability and supports overall strategic goals.³⁵

6. Methodologies for Enhancing Target-Setting

6.1. Benchmarking

A benchmark serves as a reference point for comparing an indicator, established by using current values in similar geographic areas to set targets. When selecting benchmarks, it's crucial to assess their appropriateness and achievability in the specific context, considering factors such as country-specific influences and the time required to reach benchmark levels. Benchmarking can effectively highlight progress or shortcomings and serve as a management and advocacy tool

³² USAID, "TARGET SETTING GUIDE," 9.

³³ Designing a Results Framework for Achieving Results a How-to Guide (Washington, DC: World Bank, 2012), 9–12.

³⁴ Heifer International, "Setting Targets Guidelines," 8.

³⁵ USAID, "TARGET SETTING GUIDE," 8–9.

through league tables or balanced scorecards that compare project indicators against regional benchmarks, attracting attention from the media, policymakers, and the public.³⁶

Benchmarking is a method used to improve performance by comparing an organization's current results with historical data or the results of peer agencies. This approach can involve comparing metrics, such as fatality rates, with those of similar organizations. There are three types of benchmarking: analyzing one's historical trends, comparing with peer agency results, and referencing "best in class" practices.³⁷ Using targets from similar programs to set benchmarks is crucial for understanding the contextual factors that affect performance, especially for higher-level outcome indicators. Identifying key similarities in project variables, such as policy environment, climate, and geography, is essential to ensure valid comparisons. This process should also include recognizing caveats that may impact the comparison's validity.³⁸

The choice of whom to benchmark against depends on factors such as market position and business objectives; for instance, a small business may compare itself to average sector performance, while a growth-focused company might look to established market leaders. When selecting what to benchmark, it is essential to focus on key performance drivers relevant to the sector. Accessing external benchmarking data can be challenging, but sources like trade associations and commercial market reports can provide valuable insights.

Benchmarking data should catalyze improvement, helping businesses set targets aligned with desired performance levels.³⁹

Benchmarking against best practices is a strategy for setting challenging yet realistic targets by comparing performance with industry leaders known for delivering high-quality results. This involves researching and identifying top performers, analyzing their strategies and processes, and assessing one's strengths and weaknesses against these benchmarks. By recognizing gaps and opportunities, organizations can set informed targets based on insights from others' successes and failures. This process guides target-setting and encourages continuous improvement by applying learned lessons to enhance organizational performance.⁴⁰

Targets in various industries are often established based on publicly available KPI benchmarks. For instance, the airline industry tracks metrics like on-time departures and customer satisfaction scores, while healthcare focuses on recovery rates and costs per procedure. Similarly, education measures pass rates, and telecommunications monitors call drop rates. Suppliers may highlight manufacturing order lead times, and the banking sector examines service-level agreements and cost-to-income ratios. Organizations must conduct thorough research to identify relevant benchmarks and set industry-related targets effectively, while considering regional and contextual factors that affect their applicability. Adjustments may be necessary to ensure that benchmarks are suitable for the specific circumstances of smaller companies or different

³⁶ Aneesa Arur, Mohammed-Roberts Rianna, and Eduard Bos, "SETTING TARGETS IN HEALTH, NUTRITION AND POPULATION PROJECTS" (Washington, D.C.: World Bank, 2011), 2.

³⁷ Federal Highway Administration, TARGET SETTING Component of Transportation Performance Management, 2-5.

³⁸ Heifer International, "Setting Targets Guidelines," 14.

³⁹ Info Entrepreneurs, "Measure Performance and Set Targets," 5.

⁴⁰ Performance Improvement, "How Do You Set Realistic and Challenging Targets and Benchmarks for Key Performance Indicators?" LinkedIn Community (blog), 2023, 5, <https://www.linkedin.com/advice/o/how-do-you-set-realistic-challenging-targets>.

geographic regions, as what applies in one area may not hold in another.⁴¹

6.2. *Expert Opinion (Judgment)*

This involves consulting sector experts to assess the feasibility of recommended targets for specific indicators. This requires analysts to communicate their primary analysis clearly and in non-technical terms, while allowing experts time to review it and provide informed opinions. The process includes identifying potential experts, conducting interviews to gather insights on the indicators and targets, reviewing findings, and documenting the analytical process and any assumptions made. This method is used alongside others to validate or refine targets, ensuring they are realistic and contextually appropriate.⁴²

Expert opinions are essential for determining the magnitude and timeline of targets, as these factors are influenced by political commitments, resource allocations, operational plans, seasonal conditions, and community perceptions. Typically, timelines for targets linked to the district's annual operational plans are set each year. At the same time, those for strategic planning may span three to five years, depending on the plan's duration. This expert input helps ensure that targets are realistic and achievable within the specific context of the program area.⁴³

Consulting experts is crucial for determining the feasibility and scope of indicator targets in a given context. Engaging knowledgeable individuals through interviews or group discussions allows organizations to gather insights into what is

achievable, taking into account political commitments, resource allocations, and community perceptions. This expert input helps establish realistic timelines for targets.⁴⁴ Expert judgments are a valuable resource in target-setting processes, particularly when assessing the feasibility of specific indicators within a given context. These experts provide critical input in the target-setting exercise, ensuring that the targets are realistic and aligned with the unique challenges and opportunities in the local environment.⁴⁵ Setting targets requires professional judgment that considers the local context, results evaluations, and additional data analysis.⁴⁶

6.3. *Historical Trend Analysis*

The historical trend analysis examines past and projected performance for key project-related variables using national and global statistics and data from previous projects. It is essential to assess the availability of relevant historical data for specific indicators or related phenomena, and to identify potential data sources, including government statistics and international organizations. The analysis should consider collecting multiple datasets on similar indicators to validate findings and review projected performance based on donor contributions and government budget allocations.⁴⁷

Analyzing historical trends involves examining and interpreting trend data to understand the reasons behind observed variations, thereby guiding future target setting. This process includes ensuring that major performance calculations remain consistent over time, identifying recurring patterns correlated with external trends (such as economic changes),

⁴¹ Roger Knocker, "3 Ways to Set Targets for Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)," KPI Management Solution (Kpims) (blog), December 2023, 2, <https://www.kpims.co.za/3-ways-to-set-targets-for-key-performance-indicators-kpis>.

⁴² USAID, "TARGET SETTING GUIDE," 21–39.

⁴³ Nabeela, Guidelines for Setting Performance Targets at District Level, 6–7.

⁴⁴ Heifer International, "Setting Targets Guidelines," 15.

⁴⁵ USAID, "PERFORMANCE MONITORING & EVALUATION TIPS - BASELINES AND TARGETS" (USAID, 2010), 5.

⁴⁶ Alberta Education, "Setting Targets for Education Performance Measures" (Alberta, 2018), 2.

⁴⁷ Heifer International, "Setting Targets Guidelines," 13.

investigating typical variations (such as severe weather), and recognizing shifts in trend lines due to policy changes. By understanding past results, agencies can better inform their future targets and strategies.⁴⁸

Historical trends help identify patterns of change from the past five to ten years. Analysts should look for upward or downward trends in existing reports and statistics, acknowledging that progress is often not linear. Instead of assuming consistent annual improvements, it is essential to recognize that development programs may experience plateaus or gradual progress during initial implementation phases, followed by significant advancements in later stages.⁴⁹ Historical data, such as averages or standard deviations, is essential for identifying patterns and trends that inform target setting. This approach can make target goals more realistic and attainable, especially when informed by local knowledge of current initiatives.⁵⁰

This analysis is particularly effective for evaluating an activity's highest-value outcome indicators. The process begins by confirming the availability of relevant historical data for the indicator, then identifying potential data sources, such as reports and statistics from organizations like the World Bank. After conducting the analysis, they document their findings and the steps taken throughout the analytical process, including any assumptions made. This analysis yields recommendations for annual and final targets based on historical trend insights.⁵¹ Stakeholders should reflect on their

success in achieving prior safety targets to inform future goal-setting.⁵²

6.4. Performance Evaluation Analysis

Performance measures are metrics used to track progress toward goals and objectives, helping to evaluate the achievement of established targets. These measures should be manageable, sustainable, and developed in collaboration with partners to effectively assess strategies for performance improvement. For example, a standard performance measure in transit systems is the number of passenger trips per revenue hour, which provides insight into operational efficiency. By focusing on relevant performance indicators, organizations can better understand their progress and make informed decisions to enhance overall effectiveness.⁵³

To effectively analyze current performance and set KPI, it is essential to understand the starting point. This involves thoroughly examining data and allowing time for discovery, using tools like PowerMetrics to provide an honest performance assessment. It is crucial to avoid qualifying numbers and confront the reality of performance, as setting unrealistic targets can demotivate teams. While ambitious goals, such as doubling sales in a short timeframe, may seem appealing, they often lead to frustration if deemed unattainable. Organizations can create achievable KPIs that foster motivation and progress by grounding target-setting in a realistic evaluation of past performance.⁵⁴

⁴⁸ Federal Highway Administration, TARGET SETTING Component of Transportation Performance Management, 8–9.

⁴⁹ USAID, "PERFORMANCE MONITORING & EVALUATION TIPS - BASELINES AND TARGETS," 5.

⁵⁰ The RP Group, "TARGET-SETTING STRATEGIES AND CONSIDERATIONS," 4.

⁵¹ USAID, "TARGET SETTING GUIDE," 40.

⁵² Federal Highway Administration, "Safety Performance Target Setting: State of the Practice Report" (Washington, D.C., July 2023), 35.

⁵³ Federal Highway Administration, TARGET SETTING Component of Transportation Performance Management, 4.

⁵⁴ Jonathan Taylor, "How to Set Actionable KPI Targets," Klip Folio (blog), April 2024, 5, <https://www.klipfolio.com/blog/kpi-targets>.

Organizations should build on their historical data and indicators to assess current performance and set realistic targets. Analyzing attainable growth is essential, as well as avoiding overly ambitious goals that may lead to frustration. Professional online data analysis tools can help explore performance data, enabling organizations to establish clear and achievable targets. This approach emphasizes the importance of grounding target-setting in reality rather than aspirations, ensuring that goals are based on the organization's capabilities and past performance trends. By doing so, organizations can foster motivation and a more effective pathway toward achieving their objectives.⁵⁵

6.5. Field Data Approach

Regression analysis is a valuable tool for setting targets by analyzing historical patterns and considering the impact of various factors. It can reveal that mortality improvements are often slower in countries with greater income inequality, enabling extrapolation of expected improvements across different levels of income inequality. This method is beneficial when an indicator, such as contraceptive prevalence rate, is influenced by health interventions and socioeconomic conditions. However, effective forecasting relies on high-quality data that accurately captures key determinants of trends, which can be challenging to obtain in health systems. When applying regression analysis for target setting, it is crucial to account for relevant policy and other variables to ensure that projected targets are realistic and meaningful improvements.⁵⁶

The individualized approach to setting student targets involves establishing different performance goals based on pre-test

scores, allowing for tailored expectations that reflect each group's capabilities. Students can be grouped in various ways, such as by quartiles or by significant score breaks, to create targeted growth objectives. This tiered approach allows for more focused target-setting that accounts for individual student performance, but it also presents challenges in calculations and decision-making regarding group formation and growth expectations.⁵⁷

The small-sample population approach uses a small sample size, typically 30 participants, to conduct baseline assessments and analyze patterns for target setting. According to the Central Limit Theorem, as the sample size increases, the distribution of sample means becomes approximately normal, enabling more reliable analyses. The same questions used in the baseline should be applied to this sample, and averages should be calculated for specific segments rather than the entire sample, such as focusing on the top third of scores for a particular indicator. After establishing targets based on this analysis, it is recommended that technical experts and project staff validate them to ensure their feasibility and relevance.⁵⁸

6.6. Stakeholder Expectation

Involving stakeholders in the target-setting process is crucial for success, as it ensures that targets and benchmarks are realistic, meaningful, and fair. Engaging stakeholders, including team members, customers, partners, managers, and funders, requires clear and transparent communication of the purpose and expectations. Their input can be gathered through surveys, interviews, focus groups, or workshops, and their perspectives should be integrated into the target-setting process. Regularly sharing results and achievements with

⁵⁵ Beek, "A Complete Guide on How to Set Smart KPI Targets and Goals," 3.

⁵⁶ Arur, Rianna, and Bos, "SETTING TARGETS IN HEALTH, NUTRITION AND POPULATION PROJECTS," 3.

⁵⁷ Delaware Department of Education, "TARGET-SETTING WITH DATA GUIDANCE DOCUMENT" (Delaware Department of Education, 2016), 6–7.

⁵⁸ Heifer International, "Setting Targets Guidelines," 14.

stakeholders fosters collaboration and support, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness of established targets.⁵⁹

Agencies must listen to external stakeholders to reflect their interests, build support, and integrate feedback on performance thresholds through meetings and educational tools. Minnesota's 2014-2033 Highway Plan exemplifies this: through nine stakeholder meetings and an online toolkit, it revised targets for pavement and safety priorities.⁶⁰ In setting targets for USAID activities, gathering input from stakeholders regarding their needs and expectations is essential. This involves soliciting feedback from end users and intermediate actors, such as implementing agency staff, through various methods, including formal interviews, rapid appraisals, and informal conversations. Understanding stakeholder expectations helps create realistic targets that reflect the community's desires and requirements, enhancing program effectiveness. Engaging stakeholders in this way fosters collaboration and ensures that the targets set are aligned with the actual needs of those impacted by program activities.⁶¹ Reviewing KPI targets with the project team is essential for fostering an open and honest environment where feedback can be encouraged and acted upon. While targets should be challenging to inspire improvement, they should not deflate the team's morale.⁶²

6.7. Adopt Government Targets

Most organizations have used government targets in the health and education sectors as their performance targets. Setting district targets must align with national and provincial goals,

as these targets are interrelated. Before establishing district-level targets, it is essential to consider the overarching service delivery goals and targets at the national and provincial levels for such intervention set by the national government. The ultimate data source for monitoring health services comes from health facilities, making it crucial to ensure that these higher-level objectives inform district targets. This alignment helps maintain coherence in health initiatives and ensures that local efforts contribute effectively to broader health outcomes.⁶³

Colleges can align their targets with state, district, or regional data to set realistic benchmarks for student achievement. This involves using external data sources, such as the state's Vision for Success, to establish institution-set standards and stretch targets. If a college's current rate of associate degree earners is 6%, it can compare this to the state rate to determine if it meets its minimum standard. Colleges may adopt ambitious goals, like a 20% increase in associate degree earners, based on state-level expectations. By leveraging these external benchmarks, colleges can set meaningful targets that align with local and broader educational objectives.⁶⁴

6.8. Strategy Analysis

This involves reviewing and analyzing a project's goals and strategies, often in conjunction with implementation planning. This approach is a foundation for identifying factors within the enabling environment that impact performance through contextual analysis. Key activities include reviewing the results framework (logframe), project proposals, and

⁵⁹ Performance Improvement, "How Do You Set Realistic and Challenging Targets and Benchmarks for Key Performance Indicators?" 3.

⁶⁰ Federal Highway Administration, TARGET SETTING Component of Transportation Performance Management, 17-18.

⁶¹ USAID, "PERFORMANCE MONITORING & EVALUATION TIPS - BASELINES AND TARGETS," 5.

⁶² Taylor, "How to Set Actionable KPI Targets," 8.

⁶³ Nabeela, Guidelines for Setting Performance Targets at District Level, 6.

⁶⁴ The RP Group, "TARGET-SETTING STRATEGIES AND CONSIDERATIONS," 2.

relevant goals, as well as examining underlying hypotheses and critical assumptions. It is essential to identify significant factors affecting performance in the development context, clarify the scope of coverage, and specify which population segments the project targets. This analysis ensures that projects are aligned with their intended outcomes.⁶⁵

6.9. Expectation and Accountability Approach

The method of soliciting stakeholder viewpoints on specific results and their impact on targets emphasizes the importance of accounting for political and institutional constraints that may influence targets. This process requires decision-makers from key stakeholder groups to review primary analysis briefs to understand the recommended targets. Analysts must allocate time for consultations and possess the skills to conduct key informant interviews or focus groups effectively. Analysts need to communicate the recommended targets clearly and in non-technical terms, facilitating a collaborative environment where stakeholder input can enhance accountability and target relevance.⁶⁶

The method of analyzing expectations and accountability focuses on how the expectations of donors, project participants, and other key stakeholders shape performance targets. This involves reviewing relevant documentation and stakeholder input to determine how these expectations are integrated into project goals. Analysts can account for potential political and institutional constraints affecting target setting by validating these expectations through various analysis methods. This comprehensive approach ensures that established targets align with stakeholder needs and enhance accountability in achieving desired outcomes.⁶⁷

6.10. Context Analysis

Development professionals use context analysis to review strategy documents, sector assessments, and policies, identifying how external factors, such as partner governments and civil society, affect performance targets. It highlights contextual limits/enhancers, verified through stakeholder engagement, to inform annual/final target recommendations without setting specific values.⁶⁸ Contextual analysis involves examining critical factors in the development environment that can enhance or constrain project performance. The analysis begins by identifying these critical factors and conducting a detailed review of recent assessments relevant to the project. Understanding how the enabling environment may affect performance is important, and meetings with representatives from relevant donors and government agencies may be required to validate findings. Ultimately, this analysis clarifies how various contextual elements can support or hinder the achievement of project goals.⁶⁹

6.11. Highest Possible Option

Overall Equipment Effectiveness is a metric used to evaluate machinery efficiency by combining three key elements: machine availability, operational performance rate, and output quality. This measurement helps organizations assess whether they are maximizing equipment utilization, minimizing downtime, optimizing production speed, and reducing output defects. By analyzing these components, businesses can identify areas for improvement and enhance overall productivity.⁷⁰ In other cases, if staff can only dig a meter a day, there is no use setting a target that requires them to dig more than a meter. Determining the maximum possible

⁶⁵ Heifer International, "Setting Targets Guidelines," 4.

⁶⁶ USAID, "TARGET SETTING GUIDE," 8.

⁶⁷ Heifer International, "Setting Targets Guidelines," 15.

⁶⁸ USAID, "TARGET SETTING GUIDE," 38.

⁶⁹ Heifer International, "Setting Targets Guidelines," 10–11.

⁷⁰ Info Entrepreneurs, "Measure Performance and Set Targets," 9.

level of performance can enable the team to set realistic targets.

7. Possible combination of target-setting methods.

Target setting in development practice is often treated as a technical exercise anchored in single methods such as benchmarking or trend analysis. However, the evidence presented suggests that no single method is sufficient to produce targets that are simultaneously realistic, ambitious, contextually grounded, and politically legitimate. A more robust approach lies in combining methods into coherent, theory-informed models that integrate empirical data, contextual realities, stakeholder perspectives, and strategic intent. Such hybridization reflects the complexity of development systems and aligns with established frameworks such as Goal-setting theory, RBM, and the Theory of Change. These frameworks collectively emphasize that effective targets must be specific, challenging, evidence-based, adaptive, and socially grounded.

One of the most analytically robust combinations is integrating benchmarking, historical trend analysis, and performance evaluation. This “evidence-calibrated” model triangulates three critical dimensions of target setting: external standards, temporal patterns, and internal capacity. Benchmarking introduces an aspirational dimension by referencing best-in-class or peer performance, while historical trends provide insight into realistic trajectories based on past progress. Performance analysis, in turn, grounds targets in the organization’s current operational reality. The interaction of these elements creates a “target corridor” within which goals are neither overly conservative nor unrealistically ambitious. This approach directly operationalizes Goal-setting theory, which posits that performance improves when goals are both specific and challenging yet attainable. At the same time, it

addresses a common weakness in development programming: setting targets that are either too aspirational (based solely on benchmarks) or too incremental (based solely on past trends). By combining these methods, organizations can balance ambition with feasibility.

Equally important is the integration of expert judgment, context analysis, and stakeholder expectations, which together form a “contextual realism” model. While data-driven approaches are essential, they often fail to capture the political, institutional, and socio-cultural dynamics that shape what is achievable in practice. Expert judgment brings technical and experiential knowledge, particularly on feasibility and timelines, while context analysis examines structural enablers and constraints, such as policy environments, resource availability, and institutional capacity. Stakeholder engagement adds a critical layer of legitimacy, ensuring that targets reflect the priorities and expectations of those affected by or responsible for implementation. This combination shifts target-setting from a purely technocratic exercise to a negotiated, context-sensitive process. It aligns closely with the Theory of Change, which emphasizes the importance of articulating assumptions and understanding the causal pathways through which change occurs. Without such contextual grounding, targets risk being technically sound but practically unattainable or socially disconnected.

A third important combination emerges from linking historical trends, past performance, and strategy analysis within an adaptive learning framework. Development interventions operate in dynamic environments where conditions evolve over time; therefore, targets should not be treated as fixed endpoints but as evolving hypotheses. Historical performance data provide a foundation for understanding what has been achieved and under what conditions, while strategy analysis

ensures that targets align with the program's theory of action. When combined with iterative feedback mechanisms, such as baseline, midline, and endline evaluations, this approach enables continuous refinement of targets. It reflects the principles of RBM, which integrates planning, monitoring, and evaluation into a cycle of learning and adaptation. Importantly, this model supports double-loop learning, in which not only are targets adjusted but the underlying assumptions and strategies are also revisited. In fragile or rapidly changing contexts, such adaptability is essential for maintaining relevance and effectiveness.

In contexts where sufficient data exist, more advanced combinations incorporating regression analysis, small-sample field data, and benchmarking can enhance precision. This "data-driven precision" model enables differentiated target-setting across population segments or geographic areas. Rather than applying uniform targets, organizations can establish tiered or segmented goals that reflect variations in baseline conditions and contextual factors. For example, regions with lower starting points may have different growth trajectories compared to those already performing at higher levels. This approach strengthens the analytical rigor of target-setting and aligns with RBM's emphasis on measurable, disaggregated results. However, it also requires careful attention to data quality and validation through expert input.

At the operational level, combining the "highest possible option" approach with performance analysis and expert judgment allows organizations to define stretch targets that remain within realistic bounds. This "feasibility ceiling" model is particularly useful for motivating performance without creating undue pressure or disengagement. By identifying the maximum achievable performance under existing conditions and adjusting this through expert insights and performance

data, organizations can set targets that push boundaries while remaining credible. This reflects the core principle of Goal-setting theory: that optimal performance occurs when goals are sufficiently challenging to stimulate effort but not so unrealistic as to discourage action.

Finally, integrating stakeholder expectations with accountability analysis and performance data creates an "accountability-driven" model of target setting. In this approach, targets are not merely internal management tools but social commitments that reflect negotiated expectations among donors, implementers, and beneficiaries. By systematically analyzing these expectations and validating them against empirical performance data, organizations can establish targets that are both legitimate and achievable. This is particularly important in development contexts where accountability relationships are complex and multi-layered. However, care must be taken to avoid inflating targets under political or donor pressure, which can undermine credibility and effectiveness.

8. Some critiques of the method used in target setting in the development sector

Development sector methods suffer from over-reliance on historical data, ignoring rapid changes in technology, politics, and climate; benchmarking overlooks contextual differences, local constraints, and culture; and expert opinions introduce subjectivity and bias, yielding unrealistic or conservative targets. Stakeholder and Methodological Shortcomings: Stakeholder-driven methods favor politically or donor-pleasing, inflated targets over realistic ones, risking failure and misallocation; limited systems thinking overlooks interconnections and ripple effects in development; an overemphasis on quantitative metrics neglects vital qualitative aspects for sustainability.

Linear projections oversimplify complex development systems by assuming direct cause-and-effect links and ignoring the nuances of social change; rigid methods lack adaptability to unforeseen changes or data and pursue outdated targets; and reliance on external benchmarks neglects local knowledge, yielding misaligned goals that are disconnected from community realities. Data quality issues undermine methods that assume reliable data, as developing contexts often yield incomplete/inaccurate inputs; a short-term focus prioritizes immediate outcomes over sustainable goals; neglecting unintended consequences overlooks potential negative externalities of pursuing targets.

9. Target Adjustment Gates

Tracking and adjusting indicator targets are essential for effective project management and require regular monitoring aligned with the data collection schedule outlined in the MEAL Plan. Performance indicators should be reviewed during designated learning events, and if an indicator shows adverse trends, it may necessitate further investigation and potential action. Program managers have several options for addressing these issues, including adjusting future targets, revising performance indicators to better align with expected results, or adapting the intervention based on new evidence about the theory of change or contextual factors. It is essential to approach target adjustments thoughtfully, ensuring that any changes are well-documented and reflect a clear understanding of the underlying reasons.⁷¹

Target adjustments during implementation enable learning and adaptation as new information emerges, ideally at the mid-point when context changes or approaches stabilize,

while avoiding premature or current-year alterations. Before changes, assess actual outcomes, work plan status, assumptions, resources, and stakeholder feedback; secure approvals from authorities/partners and document thoroughly. USAID exemplifies this via mission-specific annual Performance Plan and Report processes for future-year updates.⁷² USAID mission officials, with partners, approve target changes, which must be thoroughly documented. USAID staff follow specific annual processes for systematic, transparent updates.⁷³

In development projects, targets are initially set by design teams (often hastily, without broad methods/stakeholders), then adjusted three times: first by implementation teams via local consultations; second, post-baseline, to address outliers using data; and finally, post-midterm evaluation, with donor agreement for significant changes.⁷⁴

10. Conclusion

Effective target-setting for performance indicators in the development sector requires a shift from simplistic, arbitrary methods to a robust, evidence-based approach that integrates theoretical frameworks such as Goal-Setting Theory, Theory of Change, and Results-Based Management. By emphasizing collaboration, data-driven analysis, such as historical trends, benchmarking, expert judgment, and adaptive adjustments, organizations can craft realistic, ambitious targets that enhance accountability, resource allocation, and impact measurement. This approach not only addresses the complexities of social change but also fosters legitimacy and stakeholder buy-in, ensuring that targets serve as true drivers of sustainable progress rather than mere checkboxes.

⁷¹ Heifer International, 22.

⁷² USAID, "PERFORMANCE INDICATOR TARGETS V2" (USAID, March 2021), 6.

⁷³ USAID, "PERFORMANCE INDICATOR TARGETS V1," 7.

⁷⁴ Heifer International, "Setting Targets Guidelines," 7.

ii. Conflict of Interest

The author states that there is no conflict of interest.

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